

Utilizing DDR4 Memory, Intel's i9 Series, and NVIDIA's 3000 Line to Analyze the Effect of Overclocking on Performance in Relation to Power Consumption and Temperature

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Abstract

The practice of overclocking, which is the process of increasing the operating frequency of hardware components, is utilized to boost the performance levels of the hardware. This research study focused on assessing the efficiency of overclocking various components by monitoring components such as temperature and power usage. Ultimately, it aimed to determine the optimal settings for overclocking each component individually and evaluate the overall system efficiency when combining these overclocked components. Through utilizing software such as *GeekBench 6* and *3D Mark*, the study was able to benchmark the performance of components before and after overclocking to test performance. During this, temperatures and power consumption were monitored in order to determine the efficiency of overclocking the system and whether this practice provided any real benefits. With these procedures, it was found that the most efficient overclock in regards to power consumption and temperature was a 22% increase, 11% increase, and 53% increase for the CPU, GPU, and RAM respectively. In summary, this research underscores the significance of overclocking as a means to optimize hardware performance through systematic evaluation of CPU, GPU, and RAM overclocking efficiency. However, while overclocking presents tangible performance benefits, its impact on power consumption and temperature highlights the importance of integrating energy-efficient practices and environmental sustainability considerations into overclocking methodologies, fostering a balance between enhanced performance and responsible resource utilization in computing ecosystems.

Keywords: Overclocking, Central Processor, Graphics Processor, Power Consumption, Computer Performance

1. Introduction

In the current world, the transformative potential of computers continues to shape the trajectory of technological advancement and human success. With the recent proliferation of users online and the exponential growth of data, the demand for enhanced performance and efficiency from computing systems is at an unprecedented high (Allioui & Mourdi, 2023). Overclocking, a process of increasing speeds of PC (personal computer) components beyond factory functions, serves to achieve the purposes of a technology-centered

population. These include a multitude of niche sectors such as data centers for storage (Misra et al., 2022), 3D rendering applications in architectural design, and cryptocurrency mining rigs (Sukharev, 2021).

1.1 Overclocking

Presently, many PC components can be overclocked to result in higher system performance. The overclocking of a CPU (central processing unit) increases the default clock speed of the processor to execute more instructions per second. Overall system performance is boosted as a result. When a GPU (graphical processing unit) is overclocked, the clock speed and memory frequency of the graphics card are increased, which leads to enhanced graphical performance. RAM (random-access memory) can be overclocked to improve system responsiveness and multitasking abilities of a PC. In general, power consumption increases when components are overclocked due to additional voltage use. Due to the importance of optimizing computer efficiency, many recent studies have delved into overclocking on these relevant components. A 2019 study researched the durability of an Intel® Core™ i5-4670K CPU, which found that the processor's ideal frequency, with respect to performance and durability, was 3600 MHz, a 200 MHz overclock from its base frequency of 3400 MHz (Fahrizal et al., 2016). Similarly, an overclocked GPU NVIDIA® GeForce RTX 2080Ti paired with an overclocked Intel® Core™ i9-10920X chip resulted in an optimized 10.7% increase in performance (Ou et al., 2023). Additionally, a study that researched 16GB of Galax's Hall Of Fame RAM found that overclocking the RAM from 2133 MHz to 3066 MHz resulted in the most efficient performance boost in comparison to all other overclock settings (Kharisma & Putro, 2019). While these research studies have linked optimal overclocking performance to both durability and energy consumption individually, the ideal balance between durability and energy consumption while maintaining peak performance is still unclear.

1.2 Power Consumption, Temperature, and Performance Monitoring

Since overclocking boosts PC performance as a whole, it may seem to be the universal adjustment to match demanding applications and tasks run. However, a major drawback is increased power consumption and temperature, stemming from higher voltages as a direct result of component overclocking (Wu et al., 2019). Additionally, power costs increase due to the electricity utilized. A 2018 study found that adopting Turbo Boost Technology to overclock Intel processors results in the reduction of energy consumption and energy efficiency improvement in a PC (Wu et al., 2018). These researchers utilized the energy-delay product as the metric for energy efficiency and determined an average 13% improvement in it with this system. Another 2021 study utilized overclocking in smartphones to predict the thermal states of the systems (Srinivasa et al., 2021). Researchers tested an overclocking system in accordance with thermal-throttling (dynamic frequency scaling), which occurs when components reach critical temperatures and have a drastic performance decrease. This thermal-focused system identified conditions and made the correct choices 87.1% of the time. A 2023 study measured performance through the CPU and GPU with the being MHz and GHz, respectively (Ou et al., 2023). With these demonstrating a reduction of execution time and increased graphical abilities, overclocking showcases a clear difference between default settings and optimized ones. In accordance with the RAM, these can be analyzed at a deeper level. While most systems aim to maximize the saving of power and low temperatures even with performance loss, an optimal balance can be explored through the testing of the processor, graphics card, and memory.

1.3 Summary of Work

This current research focuses on finding the most efficient CPU overclock settings in relation to power consumption and temperature. Prior research has focused on memory-processor systems for optimal overclocking settings (Wu et al., 2019), and this research will consider all three components of the processor, graphics card, and memory for the highest performance with the lowest power consumption and temperatures as a balance. The greatest system efficiency with RAM overclocking is one of the main focuses, as it includes these factors. This study observes these metrics since they are an accurate indicator of system performance as a whole. Large-scale use of overclocking in computers will benefit with lower power consumption and temperatures while reaching a plateau for performance. Previous research conducted to find system efficiency in the CPU and GPU utilized outdated processor and graphics card models (Kamil et al., 2008), while this research updated the modern standards and expectations for overclocking settings using recent developments in technology. It was hypothesized that the most efficient overclock speeds in regard to power consumption and temperature for the CPU, GPU, and RAM were increased by 22% (4.4 GHz), 7% (1600 MHz), and 53% (4600 MHz), respectively. This was based on previous research conducted on overclocking PC components (Kamil et al., 2008) & (Kharisma and Putro, 2019). This experiment will allow for utilizing the optimal overclocking settings in a standard PC for maximized performance with respect to factors such as power consumption and temperature, which increase with overclocking. The individual and system efficiencies that are calculated from the benchmark scores provide an in-depth analysis of the relationships between the components and their capabilities. Research in this field of computer engineering within the industry will produce PCs that are preset to the optimal component speeds, with no need for overclocking that potentially uses more power and has high temperatures resulting in the opposite effects. In future industry manufacturing processes, these components will be built with the respective capabilities. The materials and methods used in this research are presented in Section 2, while the data is shown and analyzed in Section 3. This study's limitations and future work are also present in this section. Finally, the conclusions of this study are outlined in Section 4.

2. Materials and Methods

For this study, the PC components utilized can be found below:

- CPU: Intel® Core™ Processor i9-10850K 10/20 3.60GHz [Turbo 5.1GHz] 20MB Cache LGA1200
- GPU: MSI RTX 3070 Ventus 8GB GDDR6 Video Card
- RAM: 16GB (8GBx2) DDR4/3000MHz Dual Channel Memory (Crucial Ballistix Sport)
- Case: Corsair ICUE 4000X RGB SERIES ATX Mid-Tower Gaming Chassis + 5 AirGuide RGB fans
- Cooling: Cooler Master MASTERLIQUID ML240L V2 240mm ARGB CPU Liquid Cooler with Copper Cold Plate
- HDD: 1TB Intel® 665P SERIES PCIe NVMe M.2 SSD - Seq R/W: Up to 2000/1925 MB/s, Rnd R/W up to 160/250k
- Motherboard: ASUS TUF Gaming Z490-Plus WiFi 6 ATX, ARGB, 1GbE LAN, 2 PCIe x16, 3 PCIe x1, 6 SATA3, 2x M.2 SATA/PCIe
- Power Supply: 750 Watts - GIGABYTE GP-P750GM 80 PLUS GOLD Certified Full Modular Active Power Supply

In order to test the variation in efficiency for overclocking, the overclock with the maximum efficiency of the individual CPU and GPU components were tested to begin with (for 10 complete trials). After

this, the maximum efficiency of the whole system was tested with alterations in the RAM and the most efficient individual overclock settings of the GPU and CPU to find the most efficient system-based overclocks (for 10 complete trials). An image depicting the procedure can be seen in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1: Experimental Outline

2.1 Overclocking CPU, GPU, RAM Procedure

When overclocking the CPU, the BIOS settings were opened by restarting the PC and clicking the F2 key. After, the advanced settings menu (linked at the bottom right of the BIOS menu) was clicked. The OC Tweaker page in the advanced settings was launched, and the CPU configuration tab was clicked, with the XMP (Extreme Memory Profile) already enabled. In this tab, the setting CPU ratio was set to AllCore, and the Allcore setting was changed to the needed overclock settings. The settings of 36, 40, 44, 48, and 52 were selected to simulate the settings of 3.6 GHz (the default setting), 4.0 GHz, 4.4 GHz, 4.8 GHz, and 5.2 GHz respectively. Additionally, all the power limits found at the bottom of the CPU configuration tab were removed by inputting the highest power level possible. After this, the fixed voltage, which is found in the voltage configuration tab was set to 1.4 as a constant throughout the overclocking trials. Finally, the information was saved and BIOS was exited.

When overclocking the GPU, the *MSI Afterburner* software was installed. In this, the power limit was set to 100% in order to prevent voltage-based performance dependence. Additionally, the memory clock speed of the GPU was kept at the default of 7000 MHz to remain constant. Alternatively, the core clock speeds of the 3070 GPU were increased in increments of 50 MHz to test the ideal overclocked performance of the GPU. The tested GPU core speeds were 1500 MHz (default), 1550 MHz, 1600 MHz, 1650 MHz, and 1700 MHz. An image of the 1700 MHz settings in *MSI Afterburner* can be seen in *Figure 2*.

Figure 2: Sample Settings for 1700 MHz GPU Overclock (+200 MHz from factory settings)

When overclocking the RAM, the BIOS settings were opened by restarting the PC and clicking the F2 key. Once in the BIOS, the Advanced Settings menu was opened (located at the bottom right corner of the BIOS page). After, the memory settings option was selected to enter the RAM configuration page. In the memory settings configuration tab, the XMP was enabled to allow the RAM to run at various frequencies. Additionally, since the ASUS Z490 motherboard utilized had a maximum memory allowance of 4600 MHz, the memories of 3000 MHz, 3400 MHz, 3800 MHz, 4200 MHz, and 4600 MHz were selected to run trials on. Finally, the information was saved and BIOS was exited.

2.2 Testing Performance

When testing CPU performance, the software *Geekbench 6* was utilized to give performance readings. After *Geekbench 6* was installed, the “Run CPU Benchmark” option was selected and the testing ran for approximately five minutes. Once the testing was completed, a tab that displayed the CPU’s multicore score was opened. In this tab, additional efficiency scores for variables such as File Compression, Navigation, HTML5 Browser, PDF Renderer, Photo Library, Clang, Text Processing, Asset Compression, Object Detection, Background Blur, Horizon Detection, Object Remover, HDR, Photo Filter, Ray Tracer, and Structure from Motion were displayed.

Similarly, the GPU performance was tested with the use of *Geekbench 6*. However, instead of clicking the “Run CPU Benchmark” option, the “Run GPU Benchmark” option was selected and the process was run

for approximately five minutes. Once the testing was completed, a tab that displayed the GPU's OpenCL efficiency score was opened. In this tab, additional efficiency scores for variables such as Background Blur, Face Detection, Horizon Detection, Edge Detection, Gaussian Blur, Feature Matching, Stereo Matching, and Particle Physics were displayed.

Moreover, the system performance as a whole was tested as a whole with the use of the *3D Mark* Software. Then, by selecting the "Time Spy DirectX 12 benchmark for PCs" option, the test was started and run for approximately 10 minutes. Once the testing was completed, a tab that displayed the system's efficiency as a whole was displayed and recorded.

2.3 Testing Temperatures and Power Consumption

Since this project encapsulates finding a balance between power consumption, temperature, and performance, the average temperature and power usage were monitored during the individual trials for the CPU and GPU. The reason this was done was in order to determine the best possible clocking efficiency for the individual components prior to combining them to test system efficiency with RAM speed alterations.

When measuring the average temperature for the CPU and GPU during the trials, the *HW Software* application was utilized. A video of the CPU package temperature in the software was recorded over the interval of the benchmark, and the average temperature was taken by adding up the temperature displayed every 10 seconds and dividing it by the total number of temperature recordings taken. A video of the GPU temperature in the software was also recorded and checked over 10-second intervals to determine the average temperature in the same way as the CPU's average temperature had been taken.

Similarly, the *HW Software* was utilized to measure the average power consumption of the CPU and GPU over the trials. The average CPU power consumption was taken by recording the CPU package power over the interval of the benchmark, and the average power consumption was taken by adding up the package power displayed over 10-second intervals and dividing it by the total number of CPU package power data points taken. The GPU's average power consumption was recorded with the use of the same procedure but with the use of the GPU's power consumption rather than the CPU's package power consumption.

2.4 Efficiency Score

Once the CPU and GPU average temperatures, average power consumption, and benchmark performance levels were found, the efficiency scores were calculated with the equation seen in *Equation 1*. The equation was utilized as previous studies calculated efficiency scores with the use of placing the calculated benchmark score over the temperature and over the power separately (Kamil et al., 2008). However, since this study utilized three dependent variables, the equation set the value of the benchmark scores over the temperature multiplied by the power consumption to combine the efficiency metric of previous studies.

Equation 1: GPU and CPU Efficiency Score Calculation

Efficiency = E

$$E_{CPU} = \frac{\text{Multicore Score}}{\text{Average CPU Temperature} \cdot \text{Average CPU Power Consumption}}$$

$$E_{GPU} = \frac{\text{OpenCL Score}}{\text{Average GPU Temperature} \cdot \text{Average GPU Power Consumption}}$$

3. Results & Discussion

3.1 Raw Data with Collected Averages

Table 1: Raw CPU Benchmark Results for Trial 1

CPU Benchmark Results with Average Temperatures and Power Consumption (Trial 1)			
CPU OC Speed (GHz)	Multicore Score	Average Temperature (°C)	Average Power Consumption (W)
3.6	8872	48.6	33.0
4.0	9012	49.3	33.2
4.4	9201	50.0	33.2
4.8	9263	55.0	36.1
5.2	9228	56.0	37.5

Table 2: Raw GPU Benchmark Results for Trial 1

GPU Benchmark Results with Average Temperatures and Power Consumption (Trial 1)			
GPU OC Speed (MHz)	OpenCL Score	Average Temperature (°C)	Average Power Consumption (W)
1500	115903	42.6	51.3
1550	121603	43.2	52.6
1600	131069	44.2	51.9
1650	139721	44.4	51.8
1700	142283	45.2	56.3

Table 3: Averaged Trial 1-10 Benchmark Results for CPU Overclocks

CPU Benchmark Results with Average Temperatures and Power Consumption (10 Trial Average)			
CPU OC Speed (GHz)	Multicore Score	Average Temperature (°C)	Average Power Consumption (W)
3.6	8541	48.5	32.8
4.0	8798	49.2	32.9
4.4	9296	49.7	32.9
4.8	9361	51.0	35.1
5.2	9501	53.6	36.5

Table 4: Averaged Trial 1-10 Benchmark Results for GPU Overclocks

GPU Benchmark Results with Average Temperatures and Power Consumption (10 Trial Average)			
GPU OC Speed (MHz)	OpenCL Score	Average Temperature (°C)	Average Power Consumption (W)
1500	112971	42.4	51.8
1550	124279	43.9	54.1
1600	133812	44.2	53.8
1650	146912	44.7	52.4
1700	146712	45.2	54.7

Observing *Figures 1-4*, it can be seen that various scores were found with the use of the procedures found in *2.0 Materials and Methods*. From this, it can be seen that various metrics were found, and can be used to calculate the efficiency metrics listed in *Equation 1*. From this, the most efficient CPU and GPU overclock speeds can be found in comparison to our hypothesis.

3.2 CPU Efficiency

Table 5: Trial 1 CPU Efficiency Scores

CPU Efficiency Metrics (Trial 1)	
CPU OC Speed (GHz)	Efficiency Score
3.6	5.532
4.0	5.506
4.4	5.543
4.8	4.665
5.2	4.394

Table 6: Averaged Trial 1-10 CPU Efficiency Scores

CPU Efficiency Metrics (Averages Across Trials)	
CPU OC Speed (GHz)	Efficiency Score
3.6	5.369
4.0	5.435
4.4	5.685
4.8	5.229
5.2	4.856

By plugging the CPU Multicore Score into *Equation 1*, in combination with plugging the temperature (in Celsius) and power consumption (in watts), the CPU efficiency scores can be calculated and the hypothesis can be verified. Observing the resulting data, *see Table 6*, it can be seen that there was an increasing trend in efficiency scores until the 4.4 GHz mark (a 0.8 GHz overclock), and a decreasing pattern from 4.4 GHz to 5.2 GHz. Based on these findings, it can be seen that overclocking the CPU by 0.8 GHz provided the highest efficiency score of 5.685, correlating with the initial hypothesis.

3.3 GPU Efficiency

Table 7: Trial 1 GPU Efficiency Scores

GPU Efficiency Metrics (Trial 1)	
GPU OC Speed (MHz)	Efficiency Score
1500	53.036
1550	53.515
1600	57.136
1650	60.750
1700	55.912

Table 8: Trial 1-10 GPU Efficiency Scores

GPU Efficiency Metrics (Averages Across Trials)	
GPU OC Speed (MHz)	Efficiency Score
1500	51.436
1550	52.328
1600	56.272
1650	62.722
1700	59.339

By utilizing the average GPU OpenCL Efficiency Score into *Equation 1*, in combination with plugging the average temperature (in Celsius) and average power consumption (in watts), the GPU efficiency scores can be calculated and the hypothesis can be verified. Observing the resulting data, *see Table 8*, it can be noted that there was an increasing trend in efficiency scores until the 1650 MHz mark (150 MHz overclock), and a decreasing pattern from 1650 MHz to 1700 MHz. Based on these findings, overclocking the GPU by 150 MHz provided the highest efficiency score of 62.722, showing a slight difference with the prediction of a 100 MHz overclock being the most efficient with the initial hypothesis.

3.4 System Efficiency

Table 9: Trial 1 System Efficiency Scores

System Efficiency Metrics (Trial 1)	
RAM OC Speed (MHz)	System Efficiency Score
3000	13147
3400	13183
3800	13501
4200	13702
4600	13829

Table 10: Averaged Trial 1-10 System Efficiency Scores

System Efficiency Metrics (Averaged Trial 1-10)	
RAM OC Speed (MHz)	System Efficiency Score
3000	13193
3400	13134
3800	13482
4200	13717
4600	13906

Finally, by utilizing the GPU overclock setting with the highest efficiency, 1650 MHz, and the CPU overclock with the highest efficiency, 4.4 GHz, the most efficient RAM speed was found with the use of a full system benchmark. Observing the results of this in Table 10, it can be seen that by averaging the 10 trials, overclocking the RAM to its highest potential created the highest system efficiency score. Thus, this matched the original estimates of the hypothesis, showing a highly accurate initial prediction. Ultimately, it can be said that the collected data verifies that the most efficient overclock speeds in regards to power consumption and temperature were found to be 4.4 GHz (a 22% increase), 1650 MHz (an 11% increase), and 4600 MHz (a 53% increase) for the CPU, GPU, and RAM respectively; this shows that the hypothesis was correct in terms of the CPU and RAM, and off by approximately 4% in terms of the most efficient CPU benchmark.

3.5 Research Limitations

Several limitations are present in the current research. Firstly, the study's focus on specific hardware components, including a single model of graphics card (MSI RTX 3070 Ventus), CPU (Intel® Core™ Processor i9-10850K), and RAM (Crucial Ballistix Sport), restricts the generalizability of findings to other hardware configurations. Variations in hardware models could yield different results in terms of overclocking efficiency and system performance. Relying exclusively on benchmarking software like Geekbench 6 and 3D Mark for performance assessment may overlook crucial factors that affect system efficiency and performance, as these tools may not fully represent real-world application scenarios and diverse workload types. Moreover, the methodology employed in the study fails to consider external variables such as ambient temperature and humidity, which could significantly influence the stability and efficacy of overclocking configurations.

3.6 Future Work

Future research in overclocking efficiency and system optimization could delve into several key areas. For instance, there's a need to fine-tune overclocking settings by exploring narrower increments in frequency adjustments for both CPU and GPU in order to uncover potential optimal configurations. Additionally, investigating the impact of adjusting RAM timings alongside frequency adjustments could provide insights into further enhancing system performance and efficiency. Moreover, exploring alternative cooling solutions, advanced power delivery systems, and dynamic frequency scaling algorithms could offer more efficient overclocking strategies. Furthermore, utilizing advanced benchmarking techniques and conducting long-term stability testing can provide a comprehensive understanding of overclocking's impact on system reliability and real-world application performance. Finally, by testing various graphics cards, processors, and RAM sticks, the results can be generalized to multiple models. By exploring these avenues, the optimization of hardware configurations for various computing tasks, ultimately enhances overall system efficiency to decrease energy consumption.

4. Conclusion

This research has utilized various metrics, benchmarks, power readings, and temperature readings to determine the efficiencies of the individual components and, eventually, the system as a whole. The findings of the research demonstrate that the overclocking of the CPU and RAM by 22% and 53% to 4.4 GHz and 4600 MHz, respectively, led to the best performance of the PC with respect to power consumption and temperature. However, the GPU had the optimal efficiency when overclock settings were at 1650 MHz, which is a 10% increase from the factory speeds. This varies from the hypothesis of GPU overclocking to be the most efficient when speeds were 1600 MHz with a 7% increase. Overall, the data and results indicate that the general hypothesis of this study was shown to be correct. With the optimal speeds for the components shown in this research, the computer industry can potentially begin to produce these to be the factory settings in prebuilt systems. As a result, overclocking may not be needed entirely to optimize performance, power consumption, and temperature. Users are ensured to prevent additional power consumption and high temperatures that are unnecessary due to settings that result in enhanced performance already. This decreases the greenhouse gases that are present by preventing additional electricity generation, leading to a sustainable mitigation approach stemming from the computer field.

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